

Estimation of the Size of the Second Generation of Migrants in Russia and the West

Mariia A. Smirnova ¹

¹ National Research University Higher School of Economics (HSE University), Moscow, 109028, Russia

Received 25 August 2024 ♦ Accepted 10 March 2025 ♦ Published 3 October 2025

Citation: Smirnova MA (2025) Estimation of the Size of the Second Generation of Migrants in Russia and the West. *Population and Economics* 9(3):148-172. <https://doi.org/10.3897/popecon.9.e135459>

Abstract

The article addresses the issue of statistical accounting for the population category known as second generation of migrants. Descendants of migrants constitute a significant portion of the population in many countries, often representing a group in a vulnerable socio-economic position. Integrating this category into national statistical systems enables direct estimates of second-generation migrant populations in several countries of the West.

The study presents a critical analysis of the Russian demographic data sources, which lack specialized classifications for identifying second-generation migrants, thereby complicating reliable population estimates. As an alternative approach, this work employs cohort-component analysis to model the number of second-generation migrants born in Russia between 2001 and 2020. The model results indicate that this group is over 1 million individuals. The findings underscore the need to improve existing statistical methodologies in Russia.

This article is the output of a research project implemented as a part of the Basic Research Program at the National Research University Higher School of Economics (HSE University).

Keywords

descendants of migrants, statistical category, migrants in the Russian Federation, migrants from CIS countries and Georgia, current birth statistics, population modelling, cohort-component analysis

JEL codes: C80, C81, J11, J61

Introduction

The second generation of migrants is a special category of population statistics in many countries with high migration inflows. In several Western countries, the second generation accounts for more than 10% of the total population (Table 1), and this share continues

to grow. According to Eurostat data for 2023, there are more than 21 million members of the second generation of working age (15–64 years) living in the European Union, which is 7.5% of the total EU population of the corresponding age group; over the last two years, the number of adults belonging to the second generation has increased by 4%.

Table 1. Number of second generation of migrants in selected countries

Country	Data source	Assessment Year	Number of the second generation, million	Share of the country's population
Canada	Census	2021	6.4	16.8%
Belgium	Population Register	2022	2.0	16.4%
Netherlands	Population Register	2021	2.0	11.4%
France	Labour force survey	2021	7.4	10.9%
Germany	Microcensus	2022	8.6	10.4%
Estonia	Population Register	2021	0.1	7.7%
Austria	Labour force microcensus	2022	0.6	7.0%
Denmark	Population Register	2022	0.2	3.5%

Sources: Canada: Statistics Canada 2016; Belgium: Statbel 2024; Netherlands: Statistics Netherlands 2021; France: Institut national de la statistique et des études économiques (INSEE) 2023; Germany: Genesis-online Datenbank; Estonia: Statistics Estonia 2021; Austria: Statistik Austria 2024a; Denmark: Statistics Denmark 2024.

The second generation of migrants is becoming increasingly significant in demographic and socio-economic processes. Their reproductive and marital behaviour significantly shapes population dynamics, contributing to broader societal trends such as fertility rates, family structure, and intergenerational mobility. Furthermore, narratives about migrants and their descendants often serve as a basis for political mobilization in many European countries, making the second generation an important demographic in terms of comprehension. As members of the electorate, their political participation and preferences also shape policy directions and social cohesion. In this context, the importance of not only a realistic socio-economic and political portrait of the heterogeneous second generation but also a comprehensive understanding of its demographic behaviours and the size of its constituencies cannot be overemphasized. Such insights are critical for informed policymaking and addressing the challenges of integration and social equity.

Russia ranks among the global leaders in the number of international migrants, with a significant share of planning to settle in the country permanently (Denisenko and Mukomel 2020). This indicates that Russia's population includes growing stocks of both first- and second-generation migrants. However, second-generation migrants are not identified as a distinct category in official statistics, making it impossible to determine their numbers through direct observation, as statistical agencies in several European countries do.

This paper provides an overview of statistical sources that can be used to estimate the number of the second generation of migrants, as well as an attempt to model the size of this group in Russia based on cohort-component analysis.

The category “second generation of migrants” in national statistical systems of Europe

The term “second generation of migrants” within academic discourse can describe different populations, depending on the scope of application, the research task, and the availability of sources (Denisenko et al. 2022).

In population statistics, the term has a stricter meaning, excluding those descendants of migrants who have their own migration experience, regardless of the age at which it was acquired. Attributing an individual as a second-generation migrant requires a combination of two criteria: 1. She/he is a native of the host country (native-born) 2. One or both of her/his parents are migrants. In particular, the term “second generation” is used in Eurostat publications (European Commission. Eurostat 2011; Huddleston et al. 2013).

At the same time, peculiarities of the migration history of different countries bring differences in the definition of the second generation in national statistical systems. Even within the national statistical systems of the European Union, there are variations in the definition of the second generation. In particular, the approaches to the descendants of mixed couples in which one of the parents is a local native also differ. As a rule, the statistics of European countries distinguish the category of persons of mixed descent as a special population, but consider them as part of the second generation (as follows from the Eurostat definition and as recommended, in particular, by the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (2015). Despite its widespread use, the inclusion of children from mixed-parentage couples in the second generation has been criticized, as it implies that the migration experience of one parent outweighs the absence of such experience in the other. In some national practices (e.g., Austria), mixed descendants are excluded from the category of those with a migration background (Will 2019). This distinction is very significant for comparing the contribution of the second generation to the total population, as more than half of all migrant children in the EU are born to couples with different migration statuses (Table 2).

A further nuance that distinguishes second-generation definitions is the procedure for determining the country of origin of a migrant child in cases where the father and mother hail from disparate countries. Thus, the Austrian statistical system prioritizes the mother’s country of origin, while the Belgian system prioritizes the father’s country of first citizenship (Statistik Austria 2024b; Statbel 2024).

One of the key differences is whether or not the parent’s citizenship is included as one of the criteria. The United Nations Economic Commission for Europe’s recommendations for the 2020 round of population censuses provide for the joint recording of the attributes of the parent’s country of birth and the parent’s citizenship to identify the second generation. However, in different national traditions, the migration status of a parent may be recognized solely based on his/her place of birth (France), whether he/she has the nationality of the host country and how it was acquired (Belgium), or a combination of these attributes (Germany) (United Nations Economic Commission for Europe 2015: 137). The use of three variables at once (“country of birth”, “country of birth of the parent”, “country of first citizenship of the parent”) allows for minimizing the distortion of the second generation size due to return migration. Thus, in the case of Germany, the exclusion of the descendants of repatriates (meaning not late immigrants, but primarily persons displaced during World War II) is realized by including the attribute of parents’ citizenship at birth

in the definition of migration background. Persons with a migration background do not include the descendants of parents born abroad but with German citizenship at birth (Statistisches Bundesamt (Destatis) 2022).

Sources of Data on the Second Generation's Population Size

In global practice, the primary data sources for estimating the size of the second generation include censuses, population registers, microcensuses, and large-scale sample surveys, with the total number derived through extrapolation.

Population censuses, microcensuses, and sample surveys

In Russian censuses, as in most countries, migration status is identified through a question on the respondent's place of birth. According to UNECE recommendations (2015), this attribute is considered primary, while the place of birth of parents is secondary, and the collection of data on the place of birth of parents is recommended only for countries with a large number of immigrants living there. When the question about parents' place of birth is absent from the questionnaire, census data can identify migrant children only if they reside in the same household as their parents. The significant undercounting of the second-generation migrant stock in such a count is illustrated by the experience of Germany, which has been conducting a parallel count of the second generation in the "narrow" and "broad" sense as part of the annual microcensus since 2017 (as well as in 2005, 2009, 2013). The first category corresponds to the number of descendants of migrants living together with their parents, and the second one – regardless of household composition. The difference in the number of these categories for 2021 amounted to 1.4 million people (Statistisches Bundesamt (Destatis) 2022).

A question on parental origin is included in the expanded census or survey program, for part of the sample. In the 2021 Canadian census, questions on the place of birth and citizenship of parents were included in the expanded census form for 25% of the sample. In the U.S., questions about parental origins are asked in the U.S. Census Bureau's Current Population Survey (CPS), also in an expanded program for a portion of the sample (Denisenko et al. 2022). Germany's annual microcensus covers 1% of the population, Austria's 0.6%.

Since 2021, the large-scale European Union Labour Force Survey (EU-LFS) permanently includes questions on the country of birth of the mother and father (except in countries with small numbers of migrants – Bulgaria, Malta, Romania, and Slovakia). However, although the survey collects demographic information on all household members, most of the data is collected only for the adult population. As a result, the second-generation population estimates published by Eurostat are currently extrapolated solely for individuals aged 15 to 74 (Table 2).

It should be noted that despite the international nature of the survey, the data on stocks are not fully comparable – for example, due to the specific approach of German statistics to defining the population that can be attributed to the second generation of migrants, in the Eurostat Labour Force Survey the second generation criterion was not the country of birth (as in the case of other member states), but the nationality of the parents (European Commission. Eurostat 2011).

Table 2. Adult population (15–65 years) of selected countries by immigration status

Country	Share of the second generation in the population (1 or 2 parents are migrants)	Share of children from mixed parental pairs (only one of the parents has migration experience) in the second generation
EC-27	7.4%	57.3%
Latvia	21.00%	59.20%
Estonia	19.60%	55.10%
Switzerland	18.80%	54.60%
Luxembourg	18.40%	40.90%
Belgium	13.00%	59.60%
Germany	12.80%	52.50%
Netherlands	12.80%	57.30%
France	12.70%	53.90%
Sweden	11.40%	64.20%
Austria	10.80%	51.70%
Croatia	10.50%	67.30%
Slovenia	10.40%	66.40%
Norway	7.10%	72.30%
Ireland	6.40%	51.70%
Denmark	5.90%	63.70%
Cyprus	5.60%	76.30%
Portugal	5.60%	81.40%
Iceland	4.50%	90.70%
Lithuania	4.10%	76.00%
Czech Republic	3.90%	75.80%
Spain	3.20%	65.20%
Greece	3.10%	54.00%
Italy	3.10%	66.80%
Finland	2.80%	79.10%
Hungary	1.50%	71.80%
Poland	1.40%	72.70%

Source: compiled by the author according to Eurostat data, population by sex, age, migration status, country of birth, and country of birth of parents (Eurostat 2025).

Population registers

Population registers are the main data source on the second generation of migrants in countries where such registers are successfully maintained (e.g. Denmark, Sweden, and Belgium). Registers are considered to contain accurate and up-to-date information because the provi-

sion of access to social services and benefits is done through the register; accordingly, in addition to the obligation to report up-to-date information (in particular on movements), the population has an incentive to do so. Since family records are linked in registers, the second and third generations of immigrants can be identified based on the country of birth of their parents and grandparents. Citizenship information is also available; however, this attribute does not reliably distinguish immigrants and their descendants. If a person acquires Swedish citizenship, only this status is recorded, while any previous or additional citizenships (if applicable) are disregarded (Careja and Bevelander 2018). Registers as a source of data on socio-economic characteristics and the number of descendants of migrants have several undeniable advantages: coverage of the general population; prompt updating of data; and the possibility of longitudinal analysis in the absence of the problem of sample fudging. In terms of estimating the size of the first-generation migrant stock, registers have some disadvantages (inclusion of immigrants in the register after a considerable time after arrival; undercounting of departing migrants), but these factors do not affect the estimation of the second-generation population (Careja and Bevelander 2018).

Current birth records as a source of data on the number of second-generation migrants in Russia

Until 2010, birth statistics were compiled based on the ethnic affiliation of the parents. This approach does not allow for reliable identification of migrant parents, as it leads to an unwarranted expansion of the migrant population by including ethnic groups that predominantly reside abroad but have a long-standing multigenerational presence in Russia (such as Germans, Assyrians, Greeks, etc.). An even more significant limitation is the completeness and quality of the records, which are affected, among other things, by a large number of errors in the primary documentation of civil registry offices (Biryukova and Chudinovskikh 2011). According to the current birth records for 2010, information on the ethnic affiliation of fathers and mothers is missing in more than half of the cases (Table 3). Moreover, it cannot be assumed that the individuals who did not report their ethnicity are distributed proportionally to those who did, thus distorting the overall picture.

Table 3. Proportion of parents whose ethnicity was unknown when registering the child's birth (for selected years)

	Percentage of parents	2000	2006	2010
Mothers		10%	48%	56%
Fathers		16%	54%	61%

Source: author's calculation based on Rosstat data.

Since 2011, Rosstat (the Federal State Statistics Service of Russia) has been collecting data on the citizenship of parents as part of the current birth registration. The change in methodology has had a positive impact on the completeness of the record and on the possibility of analysing dynamics and cross-country comparisons (although the share of births for which the nationality of one or both parents – primarily the father – is unknown is quite high). However, foreigners and migrants cannot be considered identical.

In addition, the current record collects information on the parents' place of birth. This feature allows for the direct identification of migrants. These data are limited by the lack of information on the time of migration; this does not allow distinguishing between those who changed their place of residence during the Soviet period, those who came to Russia as repatriates, and those who came to Russia as labour migrants. Data on place of birth are also incomplete: in some years up to 20% of fathers and up to 10% of mothers lack information on their place of birth.

Number of children born to foreigners (2011-2022)

A total of 20.3 million births were registered between 2011 and 2022; of this number, 513.000 children (2.6%) were born to foreign-born mothers. The annual absolute number of live births to foreign mothers during this period ranged from 30.000 to 54.000 (Figure 1). The annual contribution of foreign women to total births over the entire period increased from 1.7% (2011) to 3.8% (2022).

Figure 1. Dynamics of the number of newborns in Russia, by mother's Russian citizenship, thousands. *Source:* Rosstat.

Foreign fathers were recorded for 480.000 births, accounting for 2.7% of all births where the father's citizenship is known. The annual number of such births ranges between 27.000 and 51.000. However, the absolute number of children born to foreign fathers is underestimated, as statistical data lacks information on the citizenship of 10% to 13% of fathers annually. This limitation makes it challenging to accurately assess the contribution of foreign fathers to the total number of births.

Additionally, the citizenship of both parents was not identified for 123.000 live births registered between 2011 and 2022. Since a significant number of live births cannot be attributed to specific citizenships due to incomplete data – distorting the overall picture – these cases are categorized separately (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Number of live births by parental foreign citizenship (thousands). *Source:* Rosstat.

Cumulatively, between 2011 and 2022, 203.000 children were registered as having both parents who were foreigners at the time of birth (1% of all births), and almost 783.000 children were born to couples in which at least one parent was foreign at the time of birth (3.8% of all births). The share of births in which at least one parent was a foreigner increased from 3% in 2011 to 5.9% in 2022, but this increase cannot be called sustainable since 2017 (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Proportion of births with at least one foreign citizen parent. *Source:* Rosstat.

Parental couples in which only one of the parents is a foreigner are numerically significantly larger than those in which both parents do not have Russian citizenship: considering only those parental couples whose citizenship is known, 28% of them are homogeneous

(foreign), and 72% are mixed. The latter are distributed by the composition of the parental couple as follows: 47% – only mothers are citizens of a foreign country, 53% – only fathers (Figure 4). It is important to note that the mixed nature of parental couples does not exclude the possible presence of migration experience of both parents, as statistics do not contain information on how citizenship was acquired (by birth or through naturalization).

It should also be noted that in 4% of cases, statistics contain information on the foreign citizenship of one parent, while the citizenship of the second parent (mainly the father) is unknown.

Figure 4. Number of live births to foreigners, by parental citizenship (thousands). *Source:* Rosstat.

91% of all foreign parents are citizens of CIS countries; a total of 713,000 live births were registered where one or both parents were citizens of CIS countries (excluding Russia), which is 3.5% of all births between 2011 and 2022).

The leaders in the number of children born in Russia are citizens of Tajikistan (151 thousand) and Ukraine (129 thousand). In addition to the CIS countries, citizens of Georgia (13 thousand live births), Turkey (7 thousand), China (4 thousand) and Vietnam (5 thousand) made a significant contribution to the number of births in the period from 2011 to 2022 (Figure 5).

A high share of births in mixed couples, when one of the parents has Russian citizenship, is typical for all donor countries. Slightly less than half of it is among citizens of Uzbekistan and Kyrgyzstan, in all other cases such couples prevail. The leaders in terms of participation in mixed parental couples are citizens of Kazakhstan, Georgia, and Belarus – more than 80% of young parents were paired with citizens of the Russian Federation (Figure 6). Among the citizens of countries that made a smaller but still noticeable contribution to the number of births, we can note the citizens of Turkey (almost exclusively fathers) – for them share of mixed couples is 97%. Vietnamese and Chinese, on the contrary, more often create homogeneous parental couples – the share of mixed couples is 27% and 47% respectively.

Figure 5. Distribution of live births to foreigners from 2011-2022 by parental citizenship: For cases where the mother has foreign citizenship, only the mother’s citizenship is counted; if the mother has Russian citizenship or her citizenship is not specified, the father’s citizenship is counted. *Source:* Rosstat.

Figure 6. Distribution of live births to foreigners by parental pair composition. *Source:* Rosstat.

The majority of children born to foreigners have at least one parent who is a citizen of the Russian Federation (Table 4). Among the total population, 65% registered mixed parental couples (one of the parents is a citizen of the Russian Federation), and for another 8% of live births to foreigners, the citizenship of the second parent (in the vast majority of cases, the father) was not established. Only a quarter of newborns had both parents who were foreigners (excluding couples with unidentified citizenship of the parent – 28%). Of the remaining children, 30% had only a foreign mother and another 35% had only a foreign father.

Table 4. Distribution of live births (2011–2022) by parents' citizenship

Citizenship of the parent	Number of live births in 2011–2022, thousand people				Proportion of live births in mixed parental couples (one of the parents with Russian citizenship)	Share among all foreign-born
	At least one parent is citizen of the country	These include:				
		Mother is a citizen of the country, father is a citizen of the Russian Federation	Mother is a citizen of the Russian Federation, father is a citizen of the country	Both parents are citizens of the country		
Tajikistan	153.2	48.4	36.8	49.1	56%	20%
Ukraine	129.9	47.5	51.4	20.6	76%	17%
Uzbekistan	98.6	15.7	28.8	34.8	45%	13%
Azerbaijan	82.4	30.1	26.6	18.3	69%	11%
Kyrgyzstan	80.8	26.1	13.0	26.6	48%	10%
Armenia	71.6	25.7	22.6	17.5	67%	9%
Moldova	40.0	10.8	18.5	6.4	73%	5%
Kazakhstan	36.2	12.3	16.9	4.6	81%	5%
Belarus	27.8	9.1	15.4	2.0	88%	4%
Georgia	13.5	5.5	5.8	0.9	84%	2%
other countries	59.6	7.1	38.7	11.1	77%	8%

Source: Rosstat.

Number of children born to lifetime migrants (including repatriates), 2015–2022

Between 2015 and 2022, the annual total number of births decreased by one-third, from 1.94 million to 1.3 million. However, during this period, the number of births to migrant women increased by 7.5%, while the number of births to women born in Russia declined by 25%. The most drastic reduction occurred in the category where the mother's place of birth was unknown – a decline of 92% (Figure 7). Notably, the completeness of this data significantly improved in 2019. When analysing birth dynamics from 2019 onward, excluding ambiguous data, the number of births to native-born women decreased by 15%, while

the annual number of births to migrant women grew by 5%, rising from 167.000 to 176.000. In total, between 2015 and 2022, women born abroad gave birth to 1.326 million children.

The problem of incomplete data on the place of birth significantly distorts the assessment of migrant men’s contribution to the total number of births. In 2015, the share of births with an unspecified father’s place of birth was 34%; by 2022, it had decreased to 13–14% (Figure 8).

Figure 7. Number of births by mother’s place of birth (thousands). *Source:* Rosstat.

Figure 8. Number of births by father’s place of birth (thousands). *Source:* Rosstat.

The contribution of migrants of both sexes to all births increased steadily throughout the observation period: the share of foreign-born mothers rose from 10% to 14%, and the share of male migrants from 12% to 17% (Figure 9). Most of this increase is explained by the reduction in the denominator (total number of births): in the absence of changes in the denominator, the increase in the contribution of migrants would have been about 1 percentage

point (0.7 p.p. for women and 1.1 p.p. for men). In addition, some of the increase can be explained by a decrease in the number of birth records without indication of the place of birth of the parent, but it cannot be verified.

Figure 9. Share of Births to Migrants Among All Births in Russia, 2015–2022. *Source:* Rosstat.

Migrant fathers numerically outnumber migrant mothers: for every 100 migrant men who became fathers in 2022, there are 93 migrant women, and when adjusted for the high proportion of parents (fathers, primarily) whose place of birth is unknown, there are 83 women.

Methods. Modelling estimation of the stock of the second-generation migrants in Russia

In censuses, microcensuses, and large sample surveys representative of the entire population of Russia throughout its history, the questionnaires have never included questions on the place of birth of parents. An exception is the PISA survey, but it is limited to a very specific population (15-year-olds enrolled in schools). The few special surveys aimed at the children of migrants also do not allow for extrapolation. In this context, the only viable

alternative to directly observed data is a model-based estimation of the number of migrant descendants.

For the first time, researchers in the United States began to build second-generation population models to forecast the ethno-racial composition of the population and analyse the contribution of immigration processes to the population size. The method based on cohort-component analysis was proposed by B. Edmonston and J.S. Passel (1992), who drew attention to the advantages of the generational approach. Beyond the fact that models based on generational analysis are valuable in their own right – providing separate numerical estimates for different groups of people with migration backgrounds in terms of their key characteristics – such models also enable more accurate forecasts for the entire population. This is because traditional prognostic models are based on the hypothesis that fertility and mortality parameters are the same for all generations, even though this assumption has been repeatedly disproved. Accordingly, the generational approach to cohort-component analysis incorporates distinct fertility and mortality regimes for each generation. Additionally, this method introduces models for monoracial marriages, models that account for the ethno-racial background of only one parent (typically the mother), and models that consider the descendants of mixed unions.

For Russia and the purposes of this paper, it is not reasonable to construct separate generational models as suggested by Edmonston and Passel (1992). The key differences in generational models lie in the estimation of fertility for different generations, and since the second generation of immigrants in Russia has either not yet entered the reproductive period or is at the beginning of it (even though our tasks do not include forecasting), a separate fertility model for the second generation is not necessary.

The method, based on age progression and the demographic balance equation, enables tracking changes in cohort sizes over a given time interval. At each forecasting step, corresponding to the length of the age interval (in this case, 5-year), the size of each cohort is adjusted as it transitions from one age group to the next, accounting for the effects of mortality and migration.

At each forecasting step, the following procedures are implemented (example for women):

- (1) moving the cohort into the next age group taking into account their mortality:

$${}_5P_x^F(t+5) = {}_5P_{x-5}^F(t) \cdot \frac{{}_5L_x^F}{{}_5L_{x-5}^F},$$

where ${}_5P_{x-5}^F(t)$ and ${}_5P_x^F(t+5)$ correspond to the population size of women of the same cohort in the moments t and $t+5$, $\frac{{}_5L_x^F}{{}_5L_{x-5}^F}$ is derived from a life table for women and corresponds to the probability of surviving 5-year period for the cohort;

- (2) determining the number of births per prediction step:

$$B(t, t+5) = \sum_{x=\alpha}^{\beta-5} {}_5F_x(t, t+5) \cdot \frac{5}{2} \left({}_5P_x^F(t) + {}_5P_x^F(t+5) \right),$$

where ${}_5F_x(t, t+5)$ corresponds to age-specific fertility rates for 5-year period;

- (3) calculation of the number of the first age group (those who survived to the next point in time from the number of those born):

$${}_5P_0^F(t+5) = B^F(t, t+5) \cdot \frac{{}_5L_0^F}{5 \cdot l_0},$$

where $B^F(t, t+5)$ is the number of girls born during the 5-year period, $\frac{{}_5L_0^F}{5 \cdot l_0}$ corresponds to the probability of surviving from birth to the end of the 5-year period;

(4) inclusion of mid-interval net migration with survival adjustment:

$$\left[\left({}_5P_{x-5}^F(t) + \frac{{}_5\Delta M_{x-5}^F[t, t+5]}{2} \right) \cdot \frac{{}_5L_x^F}{5L_{x-5}^F} \right] + \frac{{}_5\Delta M_x^F[t, t+5]}{2},$$

where ${}_5\Delta M_{x-5}^F[t, t+5]$ and ${}_5\Delta M_x^F[t, t+5]$ denote net female migration for age groups $x-5$ to x years over the period $[t, t+5]$, and $\frac{{}_5L_x^F}{5L_{x-5}^F}$ corresponds to 5-year cohort survival probability (transfer coefficient) for the transition from age $x-5$ to x derived from the female life table). For the youngest group (0–4) the survival ratio is $\frac{{}_5L_0^F}{5 \cdot l_0}$ (with l_0 being the life-table radix).

Population modelling is determined by the choice of the base (initial) population and the assumptions made about the components of demographic dynamics (fertility, mortality, migration). The limitation of this model is the large number of assumptions made in the context of insufficient data. At the same time, this approach allows us to make separate indicative estimates of children born in a couple where both parents are migrants and where only one of the parents is a migrant, as well as by country of origin of the parents. The same method of cohort-component analysis, but with different assumptions about reproduction parameters and a different base population, was previously used by us to estimate the number of schoolchildren of migrant origin (both with and without their own migration experience) (Smirnova 2024).

Assumptions about the base population

Choosing the cohorts whose dynamics will be tracked is one of the basic tasks in building the model. The complexity of its solution is due to the fact that the data on cohorts available to us are difficult to interpret. Data on migrant stocks are collected in the course of population censuses, primarily through the question of place of birth (Table 5).

According to international standards (European Commission, Eurostat 2011) in the context of changing political boundaries, the country of birth is the country to which the place of birth belongs at the time of the census. However, it should be taken into account that a significant proportion of migrants are, strictly speaking, repatriates. Undifferentiated analysis of migrants, including repatriates, and their descendants is questionable in terms of its meaningfulness since the incoming ethnically Russian population is virtually indistinguishable from the local population in terms of its socio-economic and cultural characteristics; including them in the stocks of the second generation inadmissibly blurs it.

Table 5. Population born outside of Russia according to the Russian Population Census 2020

Country of birth	Number (people)	Share of the Russian population (%)
Foreign countries	6 895 947	4.69
Including:		
Azerbaijan	392 575	0.27
Armenia	373 943	0.25
Belarus	348 925	0.24
Georgia	196 610	0.13
Kazakhstan	1 547 167	1.05
Kyrgyzstan	380 441	0.26
Latvia	47 498	0.03
Lithuania	33 833	0.02
Moldova	189 444	0.13
Tajikistan	422 904	0.29
Turkmenistan	105 548	0.07
Uzbekistan	843 498	0.57
Ukraine	1 686 769	1.15

Source: All-Russian Population Census 2020.

This methodological issue is not unique to Russia.. In other known cases (e.g. France and Germany – Silberman et al. 2007), in order to exclude from the second generation the descendants of repatriates from the ethnic majority and to bring the studied populations closer to more culturally homogeneous ones, the criterion of the presence of citizenship of the host country by the parent at birth is used. However, for Russia, identification of repatriates through citizenship is impossible, as such data are not collected.

One solution that can be proposed for the model is based on the analysis of migration flows after 1991. In 1992, the migration increase was fully provided by Russians; other dominant ethnic groups of post-Soviet countries showed a net outflow. Until 1995, the inflow of Russians from post-Soviet countries was particularly intensive, as it was associated with the partition of the army and the flight of Russians from the territories of armed conflicts (Population of Russia 2003-2004, 2006). Gradually, this proportion decreased but remained at over 50% until the end of the 90s. A total of 2.7 million ethnic Russians entered Russia between 1992 and 1999, accounting for 68% of all net migration; in addition, other ethnic groups traditional to Russia, especially those previously deported, such as Tatars, Germans, Koreans, and Greeks, accounted for a significant share of the migration increase (Population of Russia 2000, 2001).

Since 2000, labour migration rather than repatriation has become the prevailing trend, so it seems appropriate to assume that the accumulation of the second generation starts from this point. Thus, the chronological framework of the analysis (starting from 2000) is introduced to separate repatriates from the population of non-ethnic migrants. Migration growth differentiated by sex, age, and country of origin is taken as the base population.

Assumptions about fertility parameters

Reproductive strategies of migrants in the host country may differ significantly both from the patterns observed among their compatriots in the country of origin and from those prevailing in the host society (Kazenin 2017; Impicciatore et al. 2020). The ability to estimate age-specific fertility rates (ASFRs) of migrants is severely limited due to the challenging issue of calculating the denominator. Despite this, an attempt to estimate age-specific fertility rates of foreigners was made in the work of S. Biryukova (2013), but the ASFRs were proposed for the entire population of foreigners without differentiation by country of origin. Given the lack of data on migrant fertility in Russia, we adopted age-specific fertility rates as the average values between the rates observed in the country of origin and those in Russia.

The model assumes age-specific fertility rates as the average values between the rates in the country of origin and the rates in Russia as the low variant of the projection (1) and age-specific fertility rates corresponding to the values of the country of origin as the high variant of the projection (2). Notably, under the low projection scenario, the coefficients depend on the relative fertility intensities in the country of origin and in Russia. In some cases, the average value used for the low scenario exceeds the fertility rates of the country of origin, so it is applied in the high projection scenario.

Assumptions about migration flows

Migration growth is the only component of changes in the size of migrant populations that is directly observed and recorded in current statistical records. The cumulative migration growth from 2001 to 2020 amounted to 3.9 million people and was fully provided by the inflow of migrants from CIS countries (including Ukraine) and Georgia; Central Asia and Kazakhstan alone provided 53% of the total (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Net migration resulting from exchange with CIS countries and Georgia, by region (million persons). *Source:* Rosstat.

Assumptions about the mortality regime of migrants and their descendants

Current mortality records do not record the migration status of the deceased (only citizenship), and therefore the observed data, as in the case of fertility, cannot be used in the construction of the population model.

Since life expectancy is less influenced by cultural factors than fertility, the mortality impact was estimated using the coefficients observed for the entire Russian population. A similar solution is used in the Edmonston and Passel (1992) models, which assume that mortality does not vary across generations.

Results

Based on the above data, low and high retrospective projections were constructed, differing in the selected fertility rates. According to the models, between 2001 to 2020 (inclusive), immigrant women from the CIS and Georgia who arrived in Russia no earlier than 2000 gave birth to between 600.000 to 700.000 children (Tables 6 and 7). The majority of them (45% of the average projection) were born in the latest projection period (2016–2020) and were between 2 and 7 years old by the end of 2022. Almost as many (38% of the average projection) belong to the 2011–2015 five-year cohort; their ages at the end of 2022 were between 8 and 12 years old. 16% of children were born between 2006 and 2010. The oldest (born between 2001 and 2005), who have now reached adulthood, represents the smallest cohort (about 5% of the total estimated population).

During the next two projection periods (2021–2025 and 2026–2030), between 180.000 and 510.000 children are expected to be born to migrant women who arrived in Russia between 2000 and 2020. This calculation excludes the descendants of later migrant cohorts due to the lack of data on net migration for the ongoing and upcoming projection periods.

The presented model is based on mothers' fertility and does not include children born in families where only the father is a migrant. Meanwhile, there are reasons to assume that most children are born in mixed couples where only one of the spouses (partners) is a migrant. To realize the calculation of the number of children born in a couple "immigrant + native-born woman" within the framework of the cohort-component model, age-specific fertility rates for men would be required. Since such data are not available, the estimation relies on the necessary assumption that the ratios between the number of children born to couples "migrant father + native-born Russian mother" and the number of children born to migrant mothers are approximately equal to the corresponding ratios observed for births by parental ethnicity and by parental citizenship, that is, for overlapping but not identical populations.

For the period 2001–2010, these ratios were estimated using data on births by parental ethnicity (numerator: children born to fathers belonging to titular ethnic groups of CIS countries and Georgia and to Russian mothers; denominator: children born to mothers from titular ethnic groups, regardless of the father's ethnicity; cases with unknown ethnicity were excluded). For the period 2011–2020, analogous ratios were calculated using data on parental citizenship (numerator: foreign father and mother who is a citizen of the Russian Federation; denominator: foreign mother, regardless of the father's citizenship). Information on the number of live births by parental ethnicity and citizenship was obtained from unpublished Rosstat materials. The absence of consistent statistics covering the entire time series necessitated the use of different sources.

Table 6. Estimates of the number of children born to immigrant women from the CIS and Georgia in Russia in 2001–2020 (the low variant of the forecast, assuming ASFR values that are the average between the ASFR of the mother’s country of origin and Russia)

Mother’s country of origin	Number of births by forecast periods (thousand people)						Total
	2001–2005	2006–2010	2011–2015	2016–2020	2021–2025*	2026–2030*	
Azerbaijan	0.9	4.0	10.6	13.3	11.3	7.7	47.9
Armenia	1.1	6.0	16.2	21.4	18.9	12.9	76.6
Belarus	1.1	1.8	3.5	4.9	4.0	2.5	17.7
Kazakhstan	10.6	25.2	47.7	62.0	60.4	46.3	252.2
Kyrgyzstan	2.5	9.9	25.2	31.0	25.6	19.0	113.2
Moldova	1.1	4.1	11.5	15.0	12.1	8.5	52.4
Tajikistan	1.3	5.1	13.2	25.0	27.4	21.7	93.7
Turkmenistan	1.1	3.0	5.3	6.5	6.4	4.9	27.2
Uzbekistan	5.1	17.5	32.7	38.9	36.8	26.4	157.4
Ukraine	4.8	12.1	34.2	45.4	36.3	26.0	158.9
Georgia	1.1	3.1	6.0	6.6	5.0	3.3	25.0
All CIS countries and Georgia:	30.8	91.8	206.2	270.1	244.2	179.2	1022.3

Source: author’s calculations. Note: *For the period 2021–2030, the calculation assumes zero net migration, i.e., it accounts for children born to mothers who arrived before 2021 and excludes children born during this period to newly arrived migrant women, while maintaining age-specific fertility rates at the levels observed in 2021–2023.

Table 7. Estimates of the number of children born to immigrant women from the CIS and Georgia in Russia in 2001–2020 (the high variant of the forecast, assuming ASFR values equal to the coefficients of the mother’s country of origin)

Mother’s country of origin	Number of births by forecast periods (thousand people)						Total
	2001–2005	2006–2010	2011–2015	2016–2020	2021–2025*	2026–2030*	
Azerbaijan	1.1	4.7	11.6	13.1	11.1	7.3	48.9
Armenia	1.1	6.4	16.0	20.6	19.8	13.3	77.2
Belarus	1.0	1.5	3.5	4.8	3.7	2.3	16.8
Kazakhstan	12.9	30.8	59.5	79.6	82.6	63.4	328.8
Kyrgyzstan	3.3	13.2	32.4	40.5	33.6	24.9	147.9
Moldova	1.2	4.3	11.4	15.7	12.8	9.0	54.4
Tajikistan	1.9	7.6	17.4	33.0	36.5	28.5	124.9
Turkmenistan	1.5	4.0	6.7	8.3	8.5	6.3	35.3
Uzbekistan	6.8	23.2	37.5	47.6	50.0	35.5	200.6
Ukraine	4.5	11.2	31.4	39.9	28.7	20.6	136.4
Georgia	1.2	3.3	6.6	7.4	5.5	3.6	27.6
All CIS countries and Georgia:	36.5	110.2	234.0	310.5	292.8	214.7	1198.8

Source: author’s calculations. Note: *For the period 2021–2030, the calculation assumes zero net migration, i.e., it accounts for children born to mothers who arrived before 2021 and excludes children born during this period to newly arrived migrant women.

Ratios were calculated separately by country of origin and for each projection period (2001–2005, 2006–2010, 2011–2015, 2016–2020). For the projection periods 2021–2025 and 2026–2030, the values estimated for the most recent observed period (2016–2020) were used.

Applying these ratios to the numbers of births obtained from the cohort-component analysis, we obtain an additional 400.000 to 450.000 children born between 2001 and 2020 (Tables 8 and 9).

For the projection periods 2021–2025 and 2026–2030, the model, under the same assumptions, predicts the birth of an additional 240.000 to 300.000 children in mixed couples with migrant fathers, who arrived between 2000 and 2020, and native-born mothers.

Table 8. Estimated number of children with a migrant father and a native mother (the low variant of the forecast), thousand people

Father's country of origin:	Number of births by forecast periods (thousand people)						Total
	2001- 2005	2006- 2010	2011- 2015	2016- 2020	2021- 2025*	2026- 2030*	
Azerbaijan	0.3	1.0	5.0	7.0	6.0	4.1	23.4
Armenia	0.5	2.1	9.6	10.3	9.1	6.2	37.9
Belarus	1.1	1.9	5.2	3.8	3.0	1.9	17.0
Kazakhstan	10.1	22.7	47.0	48.7	47.4	36.3	212.1
Kyrgyzstan	0.5	2.2	9.6	9.3	7.7	5.7	35.0
Moldova	0.2	0.3	12.5	12.3	9.9	6.9	42.1
Tajikistan	1.2	4.8	7.0	10.0	11.0	8.7	42.5
Turkmenistan	1.9	3.3	4.8	3.9	3.8	2.9	20.6
Uzbekistan	2.2	7.6	29.4	17.9	16.9	12.1	86.1
Ukraine	3.6	4.9	27.8	26.1	20.8	14.9	98.2
Georgia	1.1	3.1	4.6	6.7	5.0	3.3	23.7
All CIS countries and Georgia:	22.8	53.9	162.4	155.8	140.6	103.1	638.7

Source: author's calculations. *Note:* *For the period 2021–2030 the calculation assumes zero net migration, i.e., it accounts for children born to fathers who arrived before 2021 and excludes children born during this period to newly arrived migrants.

The estimated number of children born in Russia with at least one migrant parent by 2021 ranges from 1 million to 1.15 million. By 2030, the size of the second generation is projected to range between 1.7 million and 2 million, assuming current fertility parameters remain unchanged and excluding children born to migrants who arrived after 2021.

An overwhelming number of children have only one migrant parent: based on the ratios of children born to foreign parents, only a third of children have both immigrant parents. Moreover, 65% of the descendants of migrants are related to the countries of Central Asia, with a large skew towards Kazakhstan, which accounts for almost a third of the entire second generation in the assessment covering the period up to 2021 (Figure 11).

Table 9. Estimated number of children with a migrant father and a native mother (the high variant of the forecast), thousand people.

Father's country of origin	Number of births by forecast periods (thousand people)						Total
	2001-2005	2006-2010	2011-2015	2016-2020	2021-2025*	2026-2030*	
Azerbaijan	0.4	1.2	5.5	6.9	6.1	3.8	23.9
Armenia	0.5	2.2	9.4	9.9	9.7	6.4	38.2
Belarus	1.0	1.6	5.2	3.7	2.9	1.8	16.2
Kazakhstan	12.3	27.7	58.6	62.4	67.6	49.7	278.3
Kyrgyzstan	0.7	3.0	12.3	12.1	10.4	7.5	46.0
Moldova	0.2	0.3	12.4	12.8	10.7	7.3	43.8
Tajikistan	1.8	7.1	9.2	13.2	15.0	11.4	57.6
Turkmenistan	2.6	4.4	6.1	4.9	5.4	3.7	27.1
Uzbekistan	2.9	10.0	33.8	21.9	24.4	16.3	109.3
Ukraine	3.4	4.5	25.5	22.9	16.8	11.8	85.0
Georgia	1.2	3.4	5.0	7.4	5.8	3.6	26.4
Total	26.9	65.4	182.9	178.2	174.8	123.5	751.7

Source: author's calculations. Note: *For the period 2021–2025, the calculation assumes zero net migration, i.e., it accounts for children born to fathers who arrived before 2021 and excludes children born during this period to newly arrived migrants.

Figure 11. Distribution of migrants' children- by parents' country of origin: for those born in a couple where only the father is a migrant – the father's country of origin; for the rest – the mother's country of origin, assuming cohorts of children born before 2021. Source: author's calculations.

Discussion

This research has allowed us for the first time to obtain detailed estimates of the number of second-generation migrants in Russia, which is important for both the scientific community and practitioners involved in the development of public policy. It is important to note that the data obtained, despite some methodological limitations, confirm the significant demographic effect of migration, even in the absence of official statistical records of this population group.

Interpretation of the results

Our results show that the number of second-generation migrants in Russia is more than one million. The data on the size of the second generation obtained in the course of the study are comparable to estimates of the size of similar groups in other countries, although they reveal differences in structural characteristics. This can be explained by differences in migration flows, cultural and economic conditions, and migrant policies.

Comparison with previous studies

Compared to leading European countries in receiving immigrants, the second generation in Russia remains relatively small, accounting for less than 1% of the total population. The accumulation of the second generation began only recently – after 2000, excluding the descendants of repatriates – with approximately 80% of births occurring in the last decade of the projection. By 2020, fewer than 50,000 descendants of migrants had reached adulthood, and the average age of the estimated population was just 7 years. However, the accumulation of the second generation continues, albeit at an unstable rate (in the period 2006–2010, the number of births was almost three times higher than in the previous projection period; in the next period (2011–2015), the number of births tripled again, but later the number of births, according to our estimates, remained stable). By 2030, the number of descendants of migrants who arrived between 2000 and 2020 will reach 1.9 million. Since Russia has a stable positive migration balance, including children of newly arrived cohorts, and according to the most conservative estimates, the second generation will exceed 2 million in the coming years.

Restrictions

The proposed model implies unavoidable assumptions about migrants' fertility and mortality regimes; the numbers of those born in mixed couples (to parents with different migration statuses) are also determined by indirect data; at the same time, the descendants of migrants of mixed origin constitute the overwhelming majority of the total estimates. The most difficult methodological problem is the identification of the descendants of repatriates, whose inclusion in the number of the second generation deprives this statistical category of much of its social content. The limitation of the chronological framework, which "cuts off" migrants during the mass repatriation of the 1990s, leads to undercounting the descendants of labour migrants of this period.

Reflections

The obtained estimates of the second-generation population partially clarify the scale of the challenges that need to be addressed on the way to an inclusive society. The findings have important implications for the development of public policies on migrant integration. Given the importance of the second-generation migrants for the demographic development of the country, it is necessary to develop and implement measures aimed at their integration and social support. This is especially important in the context of an increase in the number of migrants' descendants in the future.

Conclusion

The study allowed us to estimate for the first time the second-generation migrant stock in Russia, which is more than one million people, which indicates a significant demographic effect of migration even in the absence of official statistical records of this group. The use of cohort-component analysis to model the number of descendants of migrants made it possible to obtain more accurate data in conditions of limited data and to estimate the structure of the second-generation migrants taking into account their origin (by the country of origin of their parents).

The results of the study have applied value to the development of state policy in the field of integration of migrants and their descendants. The obtained estimates can be used to adjust the representativeness of samples when conducting social surveys, as well as for more accurate planning of social support measures and educational programs.

Key findings

1. The number of the second-generation migrants in Russia is significantly lower than in European countries, but it continues to grow, which requires attention from government agencies and researchers.
2. The method of cohort-component analysis has shown its effectiveness and can be recommended for use in studies of migrant stock in conditions of limited data.
3. The estimates obtained can serve as a basis for the development of social policies aimed at the integration of the second-generation migrants and their successful inclusion in society.

The study emphasizes the need for further development of the national statistical system and the integration of new methodologies for a more accurate analysis of migration processes and their long-term consequences for Russian society. This will make it possible to form a more inclusive society and create conditions for the successful integration of migrants and their descendants.

References

- Biryukova SS (2013) Methodology for assessing the contribution of migrants to the reproduction of the population of Russia on the basis of the data from civil registry. *Voprosy Statistiki* 4: 38-44. (In Russ.)
- Biryukova SS, Chudinovskikh OS (2011) Availability of data based on vital records to estimate influence of migration on reproduction of population. *Voprosy statistiki* 8: 49-58. (In Russ.)

- Careja R, Bevelander P (2018) Using population registers for migration and integration research: examples from Denmark and Sweden. *Comparative Migration Studies* 6: 19. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40878-018-0076-4>
- Denisenko M, Mukomel V (2020) Labour migration in Russia during the coronavirus pandemic. *Demographic Review* 7(3): 84–107. (In Russ.) <https://doi.org/10.17323/demreview.v7i3.11637>
- Denisenko MB, Smirnova MA, Stepanova AV (2022) Sample Surveys and Population Censuses as Data Sources on the Second Generation of Migrants: Foreign Experience. *Voprosy statistiki* 29(5): 46–60. (In Russ.) <https://doi.org/10.34023/2313-6383-2022-29-5-46-60>
- Edmonston B, Passel JS (1992) Immigration and Immigrant Generations in Population Projections. *International Journal of Forecasting* 8(3): 459–76. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0169-2070\(92\)90058-H](https://doi.org/10.1016/0169-2070(92)90058-H)
- European Commission. Eurostat (2011) Migrants in Europe: A statistical portrait of the first and second generation. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2785/5318>
- Huddleston T, Niessen J, Tjaden JD (2013) Using EU Indicators of Immigrant Integration. Final Report for Directorate-General for Home Affairs. Brussels: European Commission. URL: https://migration.gov.gr/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/CE%9421.final_report_on_using_eu_indicators_of_immigrant_integration.pdf
- Impicciatore R, Gabrielli G, Paterno A (2020) Migrants' Fertility in Italy: A Comparison Between Origin and Destination. *European Journal of Population* 36: 799–825. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10680-019-09553-w>
- Institut national de la statistique et des études économiques (INSEE) (2023) Immigrés et descendants d'immigrés en France: Insee Références. <https://www.insee.fr/fr/statistiques/6793391>
- Kazenin KI (2017) Fertility in the families of migrants: data, hypotheses, and models (foreign literature review). *Demographic Review* 4(4): 6–79. (In Russ.) <https://doi.org/10.17323/demreview.v4i4.7528>
- Population of Russia 2000 (2001) Eighth Annual Demographic Report. Vishnevsky AG (Ed). Moscow: The Institute of Economic Forecasting of the Russian Academy of Sciences.
- Population of Russia 2003–2004 (2006) Eleventh to twelfth annual issue. Vishnevsky AG (Ed). Moscow: The Institute of Economic Forecasting of the Russian Academy of Sciences.
- Silberman R, Alba R, Fournier I (2007) Segmented assimilation in France? Discrimination in the labour market against the second generation. *Ethnic and Racial Studies* 30(1): 1–27. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01419870601006488>
- Smirnova M (2024) Children of migrants in Russia: the need for integrative educational support. *Demographic Review* 11(1): 81–103. (In Russ.) <https://doi.org/10.17323/demreview.v11i1.20933>
- United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (2015) Conference of European Statisticians Recommendations for the 2020 Censuses of Population and Housing. United Nations, New York and Geneva. URL: https://unece.org/DAM/stats/publications/2015/ECECES41_EN.pdf
- Will AK (2019) The German statistical category 'migration background': Historical roots, revisions and shortcomings. *Ethnicities* 19(3): 535–557. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1468796819833437>

Other sources of information

- All-Russian Population Census 2020. Results of the 2020 Census. Volume 6: Population Migration. Table 1: Population by Place of Birth and Place of Residence in the Russian Federation by Federal Subjects. https://rosstat.gov.ru/vpn/2020/Tom6_Migraciya_naseleniya
- Eurostat Database (<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/data/database>)
- GENESIS-Online (<https://www-genesis.destatis.de/datenbank/online>)

- Statbel (2024) Origin. <https://statbel.fgov.be/en/themes/population/structure-population/origin#documents>
- Statistics Canada (2022) Table 98-10-0338-01 Ethnic or cultural origin by generation status: Canada, provinces and territories, census metropolitan areas and census agglomerations with parts. <https://doi.org/10.25318/9810033801-eng>
- Statistics Denmark (2024) Population 1. January by parish, ancestry. www.statbank.dk/KMSTA001
- Statistics Estonia (2021) RL21521: Population by sex, ethnicity, country of birth, and parents' country of birth, 31 December 2021. https://andmed.stat.ee/en/stat/rahvaloendus__rel2021__pelisus-jaranne__polis-ja-valisparitolu-rahvastik/RL21521
- Statistics Netherlands (2021) Population Dashboard. Origin. <https://www.cbs.nl/en-gb/visualisations/dashboard-population/origin>
- Statistik Austria (2024a) Migrationshintergrund. <https://www.statistik.at/statistiken/bevoelkerung-und-soziales/bevoelkerung/migration-und-einbuengerung/migrationshintergrund>
- Statistik Austria (2024b) Mikrozensus-Arbeitskräfteerhebung (Durchschnitt aller Wochen eines Jahres). <https://www.statistik.at/statistiken/bevoelkerung-und-soziales/bevoelkerung/migration-und-einbuengerung/migrationshintergrund>
- Statistisches Bundesamt (Destatis) (2022) Bevölkerung und Erwerbstätigkeit. Bevölkerung mit Migrationshintergrund: Ergebnisse des Mikrozensus 2021. https://www.destatis.de/DE/Themen/Gesellschaft-Umwelt/Bevoelkerung/Migration-Integration/Publikationen/Downloads-Migration/migrationshintergrund-2010220217004.pdf?__blob=publicationFile

Acknowledgments

This work is the output of a research project implemented as part of the Basic Research Program at the National Research University Higher School of Economics (HSE University).

Information about the author

- Mariia Alekseevna Smirnova – PhD student, Doctoral School of Sociology, National Research University Higher School of Economics. Moscow, 109028, Russia. E-mail: mariaus@bk.ru